

Spiro Heterocycles. Part-VII. Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of some Fluorine containing Spiro[azetidine-2,3'-[3H]indole]-2',4(1'H)-diones

KRISHNA C. JOSHI*, RENUKA JAIN and VANDANA SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

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Several new fluorine containing spiro [azetidine-2,3'-[3H]indole]-2',4(1'H)-diones have been synthesised by the condensation of chloroacetylchloride with Schiff bases of indole-2,3-diones. The structures are supported by analysis, ir and nmr spectra, and some of the compounds have been screened for antibacterial activity.

THE β -lactam drugs are the most widely prescribed antibiotics used in medicine even after many years of their introduction¹⁻³. The naturally occurring azetidine-2-carboxylic acid has shown some unique and potentially useful biological activities⁴⁻⁷. Some *o*-toluidine derivatives also show bacteriostatic and antifungal activity. In view of our recent interest in indoles with C-3 as spiro atom⁸ and recalling that various classes of these compounds, viz. Fredricamycin A display pronounced biological activities including antitumor-antibiotic activity, we have now incorporated azetidine moiety into indole nucleus and synthesised several fluorine containing spiro[azetidine-2,3'-[3H]indole]-2',4(1'H)-diones and screened them for antibacterial activity. In this, we have been further guided by the observation that incorporation of fluorine into bioactive molecules can lead to altered/enhanced biological activity.

The synthesis involved the condensation of primary amines with an appropriate indole-2,3-dione (1) resulting in the formation of the intermediate Schiff bases (2) which on cyclocondensation with chloroacetylchloride gave the spiro product (3) (Scheme 1). The formation of these compounds is evidenced by ir and nmr spectral studies. In the ir spectra, absorptions at 1700 (C=O) and 1650 cm^{-1} (C=N stretching) indicated the formation of 3-aryliminoindole-2-ones. Ir spectra of the final spiro compound showed disappearance of C=N absorption and appearance of absorptions at

1710 cm^{-1} (monocyclic β -lactam ring) and 745-770 cm^{-1} (C-Cl group). The indole carbonyl absorption remained as such. In the nmr spectra of the spiro compound, additional peak due to C-H proton at δ 4.2 was observed along with usual absorptions of aromatic protons in the region δ 7.3-7.9 and NH proton at δ 8.4.

Experimental

The purity of compounds was checked by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer RB-12 and Varian A-60D instruments. TMS was taken as internal standard for pmr spectra.

3-Aryliminoindol-2-ones; Schiff bases (2): These were prepared following the method of Joshi *et al.*⁹ by the condensation of appropriate indole-2,3-diones with aromatic amines.

3-Chloro-5'-fluoro-1-(4-fluorophenyl)-spiro[azetidine-2,3'-[3H]indole]-2',4(1'H)-diones (3): To a well stirred solution of 5-fluoro-3-(4-fluorophenyl)iminoindol-2-one (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.01 mol) in dry benzene was added chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mol) dropwise at room temperature¹⁰. After addition of chloroacetyl chloride was complete, the mixture was stirred for extra 5 h and left at room temperature for 3 days. The precipitated triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered off and washed thoroughly with dry benzene. The filtrate was washed several times with dilute hydrochloric acid, then with water and then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was evaporated *in vacuo* and the residue was then recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (70%), m.p. 140°.

Other spiro[azetidine-2,3'-[3H]indole]-2',4(1'H)-diones (3) were prepared in a similar manner. Their characterisation data are recorded in Table 1.

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF SPIRO[AZETIDINE-2,3'-[3H]INDOLE]-2',4(1'H)-DIONES (3)

Sl. no.	X	R	R'	Mol formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen % Found/(Calcd.)
1.	H	4-FC ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClFN ₂ O ₂	115	55	8.77 (8.84)
2.	5-F	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClFN ₂ O ₂	136	60	8.70 (8.84)
3.	5-F	4-FC ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₆ H ₉ ClF ₂ N ₂ O ₂	140-142	70	8.28 (8.37)
4.	5-F	3-FC ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₆ H ₉ ClF ₂ N ₂ O ₂	95	40	8.30 (8.37)
5.	5-F	4-CF ₃ C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₇ H ₉ ClF ₃ N ₂ O ₂	74	50	7.19 (7.26)
6.	5-F	4-FC ₆ H ₄	CH ₂ N	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ ClF ₂ N ₃ O ₂	105	48	9.65 (9.68)
7.	6-F	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClFN ₂ O ₂	98	50	8.80 (8.84)
8.	6-F	4-FC ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₆ H ₉ ClF ₂ N ₂ O ₂	103	45	8.82 (8.37)
9.	6-F	4-CF ₃ C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₇ H ₉ ClF ₃ N ₂ O ₂	78	60	7.22 (7.26)

Antibacterial activity :

The compounds (Table 1) were tested for antibacterial activity against gram-negative bacteria, viz. *E. coli*, *P. pyocyneus*, *C. frundii* and gram-positive bacteria, viz. *S. coagulase*, *S. viridaus* and *S. hemolyticus* by disc method¹¹, using ethanol as a solvent at a concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹. The observations indicate that the compounds are not active against gram-negative bacteria except compounds of serial nos. 2, 3, 5 and 9 which show slight activity against *E. coli* (zone of inhibition between 7-10 mm in diameter). All the compounds are, however, moderately active against gram-positive bacteria (zone of inhibition between 10-17 mm), the activity against *S. hemolyticus* is maximum.

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